

Isolation of Phenolics from Leaves of *Terminalia arjuna*

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Apigenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside, gallic and ellagic acids have been isolated from methanol extract of the leaves of *Terminalia arjuna*.

The distribution of phenolics in leaves has been implicated as taxonomical guide¹ and biosynthetic precursors of phenolics in heartwood, bark, root and other tissues of the plants². The leaves of *Terminalia arjuna* and *T. tomentosa* are the primary food plants of tropical tasar silkworm *Antheraea mylitta*³. The simple phenolic precursors isoquercetin and morin from primary food plant of *Bombyx mori* act as feeding attractants⁴, whereas polymeric phenolic precursors, soluble and complex tannins from *Quercus robur* act as feeding deterrent to winter Moth and other insects⁵. Although the phenolics from heartwood⁶, bark⁷⁻⁹ and root¹⁰ of above primary food plants have been isolated to identify the medicinally active phenolics from above plants, but the isolation of phenolics from leaves of *T. arjuna* is not reported in relation to its feeding attractant and feeding deterrent effect to tasar silkworm¹¹. We report here the isolation of phenolics from methanol extract of dry leaves of *T. arjuna* to understand the roles of plant phenolics in plant-herbivore interactions.

The pruned leaves of *T. arjuna* was defatted with petroleum ether and marc left was extracted with hot methanol¹². The methanol extract was concentrated and the residue chromatographed on silica gel to give apigenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside (**1**). The structure of **1** was confirmed by electronic, ir, nmr and FABMS.

Apigenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside (**1**)

This constitutes the first isolation of **1** from the leaves of the plant. Further elution of column with benzene-ethyl acetate with increasing polarity ratio gave gallic acid and ellagic acid, whose structures were confirmed by m.m.p., superimposable ir and formation of their methyl ester derivatives.

Further, highly oxygenated flavanoids⁶, ellagic acid derivatives^{13,14} and tannins¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have been isolated from leaves, bark, heartwood and roots of *Terminalia* genus. Preliminary structure correlation indicates that simple phenolics from leaves might be precursors for complex phenolics from other tissues of *Terminalia* genus.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Thomas-Hoover-Unimelt apparatus and are uncorrected. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-260 spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Jeol JMX-200 (200 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and FABMS on a Jeol SX-102/DA-6000 spectrometer using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 ml) as FAB gas and *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol (NBA) as the matrix.

The mature dry leaves of *T. arjuna* (1 kg) (taken from pollarded trees grown at experimental station of the Central Tasar Silk and Training Institute, Ranchi) were extracted with hot methanol for 56 h after being defatted with petroleum ether extract¹². The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and chromatographed on a silica gel column eluted with benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate and ethyl acetate. The elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (50 : 50) yielded a yellow compound (100 mg), which gave green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and positive to Molish and Shinoda (Mg/HCl) tests. It was found to be apigenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside, m.p. 198° (lit.¹⁸ 198°); *R_f* (B : A : W, 5 : 1 : 4), 0.86; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400, 1650, 1600, 1560, 1355 and 1170 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 266, 366 nm, (compd. + AlCl₃) 296, 390 nm, (compd. + NaOMe) 271, 304, 390 nm, (compd. + NaOAc) 266, 336 nm; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) [aglycone moieties] 13.15 (s, OH-5), 8.01 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-2',6'), 6.89 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3',5'), 6.90 (d, H-8), 6.76 (d, H-6), 6.26 (s, H-3), [sugar moieties] (glu) 5.12 (d, *J* 6.8 Hz, H-1), (rha) 4.94 (d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-1), 3.22-4.24 (m, 15-H, rhamnoglucoside), 1.15 (d, *J* 6.2 Hz, rha, methyl); FABMS *m/z* 578 [M]⁺, 432 [M-146]⁺, 270 [M-146-162]⁺, 153 and 118.

Apigenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside (50 mg) was hydrolyzed with 10% methanolic H₂SO₄ for 8 h to yield a pale yellow aglycone, apigenin, m.p. 345° (lit.¹⁹ 346°); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 269, 336 nm; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 12.90 (s, OH-5), 7.96 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2',6'), 6.98 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3',5'), 6.76 (d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.5 (s, H-3), 6.25 (d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6); FABMS *m/z* 270 [M⁺, 100%], 269 (17%), 242 (12%), 153 (10%), 124 (10%) and 118 (10%).

The hydrolysate was neutralized with BaCO₃. The neutralized solution was paper chromatographed and *R_f* value was comparable to glucose and rhamnose (0.18 and 0.34 respectively) in solvent system butanol-acetic acid-water, (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) and co-chromatography with authentic samples.

NOTE

The elution of column with benzene-ethyl acetate (50 : 50) gave gallic acid. It gave blue color with ferric chloride, m.p. 240° (lit.²⁰ 243–5°); R_f (B : A : W 4 : 1 : 5) : 0.62; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 280 nm; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3225, 2900, 1695, 1600, 1520, 1450, 1365, 1330, 1295, 1220 and 1000 cm^{-1} . It was confirmed by preparing methyl gallate, m.p. 198° (lit.²¹ 196°).

Further elution of column with ethyl acetate gave elagic acid, crystallized from dioxane. It gave green color with ferric chloride in ethanol, m.p. >300° (lit.⁷ >300°); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 255, 366 nm; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3570, 3490, 1730, 1625, 1585 and 1540 cm^{-1} . It was confirmed by preparation of tetra-*O*-methylelagic acid, m.p. 340° (lit.⁷ 341–2°).

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